

**New and rare weevils in Hungary II.
(Coleoptera: Curculionoidea)**

Valentin SZÉNÁSI

Duna-Ipoly National Park Directorate, H-1021 Budapest, Költő utca 21, Hungary.

E-mail: szvalent@gmail.com

Abstract – Distribution data are presented for several species of weevils (Coleoptera: Brentidae, Curculionidae) from Hungary. *Ceutorhynchus viridanus* Gyllenhal, 1837, *Miarus ursinus* Abeille de Perrin, 1906, *Otiorhynchus ovalipennis* Boheman, 1842, *Otiorhynchus ropotamus* Angelov, 1974, and *Pachyrhinus lethierryi* (Desbrochers des Loges, 1875) are first recorded from the country. Additionally, recent, unpublished Hungarian records of *Alcidodes karelinii* (Boheman, 1844), *Ceratapion armatum* (Gerstaecker, 1854), *Curculio gyongyiae* Szénási, 2022, *Gronops lunatus* (Fabricius, 1775), *Herpes porcellus* (Lacordaire, 1863), *Hypera libanotidis* (Reitter, 1896), *Loborhynchapion amethystinum* (Miller, 1857), *Otiorhynchus coarctatus* Stierlin, 1861, *Otiorhynchus juglandis* Apfelbeck, 1895, *Otiorhynchus lutosus* Stierlin, 1858, *Otiorhynchus roubali* Penecke, 1931, *Otiorhynchus winkleri* F. Solari, 1937 and *Polydrusus crinipes* Germann, 2018 are presented.

Key words – faunistics, new country records

INTRODUCTION

The author and his friends are involved in various conservation projects, and during the fieldwork they have the possibility to collect and study the weevil fauna of different areas in Hungary. This paper presents records of some rare or recently discovered species, including five which are new to the country, and raises the total species number of Curculionoidea of Hungary to 1231 (PODLUSSÁNY *et al.* 2019, PODLUSSÁNY & VIG 2022, SZÉNÁSI 2020). All specimens were identified by the author. The reported specimens are deposited partly in the private collection of Valentin Szénási (CVS, Isaszeg, Hungary), and partly in the Hungarian Natural History Museum (HNHM, Budapest, Hungary).

SPECIES NEW TO HUNGARY

Ceutorhynchus viridanus Gyllenhal, 1837
(Fig. 1)

Material examined – **Pest County:** Budaörs, Farkas-hill, 26.V.2017, leg. O. Merkl (1 female, HNHM).

Notes – The species occurs in Europe, Middle Asia and Turkey (Asian Territory) (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2017). First record for Hungary. Proposed Hungarian name: kékes repcsény-ceutormányos.

Miarus ursinus Abeille de Perrin, 1906
(Fig. 2)

Material examined – **Győr-Moson-Sopron County:** Koroncó, along Marcal river, 27.V.2021, leg. B. Szelenczey (1 male, CVS).

Notes – The species occurs in Europe (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2017). First record for Hungary. Proposed Hungarian name: déli harangvirág-ormányos.

Otiorhynchus ovalipennis Boheman, 1842
(Fig. 3)

Material examined – **Pest County:** Dunakeszi, Ábrahám Pál street 48/b, from Leyland cypress (*Cupressus* × *leylandii* A. B. Jacks et Dall.), 12.V.2022, 2.VI.2022, 10.VI.2022, 12.VI.2022, 30.VIII.2022, 30.IX.2022, leg. A. Kotán (3 specimens, HNHM; 48 specimens, CVS).

Notes – The species occurs in South Europe, the Middle East, and the Caucasus (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2017). First record for Hungary. Proposed Hungarian name: balkáni gyalogormányos.

Otiorhynchus ropotamus Angelov, 1974
(Fig. 4)

Material examined – **Budapest:** District XXII, Kamaraerdei street 8, 4.VI.2020, leg. M. Lukátsi (1 female, CVS). **Pest County:** Budafok, Falka street, 20.IX.2021, leg. M. Lukátsi (1 female, CVS); Pilisborosjenő, Kövesbérc, 20.I.2014, 18.V.2014, leg. T. Németh (2 females, HNHM, published as *Otiorhynchus smreczynskii* in PODLUSSÁNY *et al.* (2014)).

Notes – The species was known only from Bulgaria (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2017). First records for Hungary. A photo of another specimen, taken in Csongrád-Csanád County, Domaszék, near Móraszék, on 14.IX.2022, by L. Lajtár, uploaded to the online citizen science platform [izeltlabuak.hu](https://www.izeltlabuak.hu)*, pertains to this species. Proposed Hungarian name: bolgár gyalogormányos.

Figs 1–5. 1 = *Ceutorhynchus viridanus* Gyllenhal, 1837, 2 = *Miarus ursinus* Abeille de Perrin, 1906, 3 = *Otiorhynchus ovalipennis* Boheman, 1842, 4 = *Otiorhynchus ropotamus* Angelov, 1974, 5 = *Pachyrhinus lethierryi* (Desbrochers des Loges, 1875) (photos by Valentin Szénási (Figs 1–4), and Aranka Grabant (Fig. 5))

* <https://www.izeltlabuak.hu/talalat/322430>

Pachyrhinus lethierryi (Desbrochers des Loges, 1875)
(Fig. 5)

Material examined – **Budapest**: District II, Budai Kertcentrum, 9.IV.2018, leg. D. Horváth (1 female, HNHM).

Notes – This South European species is expanding in range, and was found in several European countries in the recent years (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2017). First record for Hungary. Photos of another specimens, taken in Baranya County, Pécs, Botanical Garden, on 28.IV.2022, by K. Németh, in Csongrád-Csanád County, Szeged, near the Kisstadion, on 3.VI.2022, by M. A. Remete, in Hajdú-Bihar County, Balmazújváros, Akác köz, on 22.V.2020, by V. Zsupos, and in Pest County, Pilisborosjenő, Malomdűlő, on 16.V.2021, by G. Keresztes, uploaded to the online citizen science platform izeltlabuak.hu**, pertain to this species. Proposed Hungarian name: tujarontó ormányos.

NEW RECORDS OF RARE OR EXPANDING SPECIES

Alcidodes karelinii (Boheman, 1844)

Material examined – **Bács-Kiskun County**: Dunatetőtlen, Böddi-szék, 26.VI.2021, leg. V. Szénási (1 specimen, CVS); Kiskőrös, Kossuth Lajos street, 29.III.2021, on sweet peppers from foil, leg. G. Dömsödi (1 specimen, CVS); Kunpeszér, near Dunavölgyi main canal, 25.VII.2022, leg. V. Szénási (1 specimen, CVS). **Csongrád-Csanád County**: Domaszék, Móra-szék, 7.VII.2022, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens, CVS). **Pest County**: Abony, near the road no. 4, 9.VIII.2021, and Füzes-ér-dűlő, 9.VIII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (6 specimens, CVS); Bugyi, Kender-földek, 13.VIII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens, CVS), and near Vastag-hill, 25.VII.2022, leg. V. Szénási (4 specimens, CVS); Cegléd, along the Perje main canal, 9.VIII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens, CVS); Dabas, near canal no. 20, 25.VII.2022, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens, CVS), and Kis-Földek, 25.VII.2022, leg. V. Szénási (6 specimens, CVS); Kiskunlacháza, quarry ponds, 13.VIII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens, CVS); Körösetetőtlen, along the Perje main canal, 9.VIII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens, CVS); Kocsér, near Józantanya, 9.VIII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (5 specimens, CVS); Jászkarajenő, Nyilas-canal, 9.VIII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens, CVS); Nagykovács, Alsó-járás, 9.VIII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (1 specimen, CVS); Ócsa, near Duna-Tisza-canal,

** <https://www.izeltlabuak.hu/talalat/255501>, <https://www.izeltlabuak.hu/talalat/272742>, <https://www.izeltlabuak.hu/talalat/122829>, <https://www.izeltlabuak.hu/talalat/245498>, respectively

13.VIII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens, CVS), and Öreg-hill, 13.VIII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens, CVS); Tatárszentgyörgy, Rohanka-dűlő, 25.VII.2022, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens, CVS).

Notes – The species occurs in Europe (southern Russia, Ukraine) and the Far East (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2017). The species was recorded as new to Hungary in 2019 (SZÉNÁSI & VÁRI 2019), it has since been expanding at a rapid pace.

Ceratapion armatum (Gerstaecker, 1854)

Material examined – **Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County:** Bököny, Közösléglő, 3.VI.2022; 13.VI.2022, leg. N. Tóth (2 specimens, CVS).

Notes – The species occurs in Europe and the Caucasian Region (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2017). Very rare in Hungary.

Curculio gyongyiae Szénási, 2022

Material examined – **Pest County:** Domony, Faház-tető, 10.VIII.2022, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens, CVS); Isaszeg, Kunyhó-nyiladék, 5.IX.2022, leg. V. Szénási (1 specimen, CVS); Nagymaros, Rigó-hill, 2.VIII.2022, leg. T. Németh (1 specimen, CVS). **Komárom-Esztergom County:** Vértestolna, Pes-kő, 2.VIII.2022, leg. V. Szénási (1 specimen, CVS). **Veszprém County:** Balatonakali, Magyal, 13.VIII.2022, leg. V. Szénási (1 specimen, CVS); Balatonalmádi, Megye-hill, 13.VIII.2022, leg. V. Szénási (1 specimen, CVS); Balatonederics, Szabó-pince, 25.VII.2022, leg. A. Kotán (1 specimen, CVS); Örvényes, Fáslegelő, 13.VIII.2022, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens, CVS).

Notes – The species is so far known from Croatia, Greece and Hungary (SZÉNÁSI 2022).

Gronops lunatus (Fabricius, 1775)

Material examined – **Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County:** Bököny, Közösléglő, 20.VI.2021, leg. N. Tóth (1 specimen, CVS).

Notes – The species occurs in Europe and North Africa (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2017). Very rare in Hungary.

Herpes porcellus (Lacordaire, 1863)
(Fig. 6)

Material examined – **Pest County:** Tatárszentgyörgy, near canal no. 20, 17.X.2020, leg. V. Szénási (1 specimen, CVS).

Notes – Collected from a new host plant in Hungary: common bugloss (*Anchusa officinalis* L.) (Boraginaceae). The specimen on Fig. 6 does not pertain to the reported record.

Fig. 6. *Herpes porcellus* (Lacordaire, 1863) (photo by Annamária Csóka)

Hypera libanotidis (Reitter, 1896)

Material examined – **Veszprém County:** Balatonkenese, Soós-hill, 20.II.2021, leg. V. Szénási (6 specimens, CVS, 2 specimens, HNHM), and Tujasor, 26.II.2021, leg. V. Szénási (1 specimen, CVS); Balatonszepezd, near Szűcs-hill, 6.III.2021, 29.I.2022, 10.II.2022, leg. V. Szénási (8 specimens, CVS); Balatonszőlős near Nagy-Gella, 2.III.2021, leg. A. Mészáros, V. Szénási (4 specimens, CVS); Pécsely, Derék-hill, 11.III.2021, leg. A. Mészáros, V. Szénási (2 specimens, CVS), and Öreg-hill, 4.VII.2020, 21.VIII.2020, 4.VI.2021, leg. V. Szénási (4 specimens, CVS), 2.I.2021, 6.II.2021, 26.II.2021, leg. A. Kotán, V. Szénási (5 specimens, CVS); Szentkirályszabadja, Vödör-valley, 2.III.2021, leg. A. Mészáros, V. Szénási

(2 specimens, CVS); Zalahaláp, near Halápi-hill, 6.III.2021, leg. V. Szénási (4 specimens, CVS); Latonya, 11.III.2021, leg. A. Mészáros, V. Szénási (3 specimens, CVS); Újdörögdpuszta, 13.III.2021, leg. V. Szénási (4 specimens, CVS); Zánka, near Szücs-hill, 6.III.2021, leg. V. Szénási (6 specimens, CVS).

Notes – The species occurs in the Czech Republic and Hungary (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2017). Very rare in Hungary.

Loborhynchapion ametysthinum (Miller, 1857)

Material examined – **Békés County:** Battonya, Kistompapuszta löszgyep, 15.V.2020, leg. V. Szénási (1 specimen, CVS).

Notes – The species occurs in Europe, Middle East, and Middle Asia (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2017). Very rare in Hungary.

Otiorhynchus coarctatus Stierlin, 1861

Material examined – **Komárom-Esztergom County:** Lábatlan, Nagy-Pisznice, 6.X.2022, leg. V. Szénási (1 specimen, CVS).

Notes – The species occurs in Europe (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2017). Rare in Hungary.

Otiorhynchus juglandis Apfelbeck, 1895

Material examined – **Komárom-Esztergom County:** Vérttestolna, Peskő, 30.XII.2020, leg. A. Kotán (1 specimen, CVS), 2.VIII.2022, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens, CVS).

Notes – The species occurs in Europe (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2017). Very rare in Hungary, only two old records have been known (Budapest, Vadaskert, 1938, leg. Csiki (2 specimens, HNHM); Budapest, 1944, leg. Kuthy (1 specimen, HNHM)).

Otiorhynchus lutosus Stierlin, 1858

Material examined – **Győr-Moson-Sopron County:** Dénesfa, Cseri-legelő, 2.VII.2021, 5.VII.2021, 30.IX.2021, leg. A. Kotán, V. Szénási (2 specimens, CVS).

Notes – The species occurs in Europe (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2017). Very rare in Hungary, only one old record has been known (Pinnye, 1944, leg. Streda (4 specimens, HNHM)).

Otiorhynchus roubali Penecke, 1931

Material examined – **Veszprém County:** Csesznek, Gézaházapuszta, 6.IX.2020, leg. B. Szelenczey (1 specimen, CVS).

Notes – The species occurs in Hungary, Romania and Slovakia (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2017). Very rare in Hungary, so far known only from the Gömör-Torna Karst region.

Otiorhynchus winkleri F. Solari, 1937

Material examined – **Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén County:** Füzér, Vár-hill, 26.VI.2020, leg. R. Vidéki (1 specimen, CVS).

Notes – The species occurs in Europe (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2017). Very rare in Hungary, only a few records have been known from the Bükk Mountains.

Polydrusus crinipes Germann, 2018

Material examined – **Bács-Kiskun County:** Lajosmizse, railway station, 26.VII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens, CVS); Kecskemét, along road no. 5, 26.VII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (4 specimens, CVS), and Air Base, 26.VII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens, CVS). **Csongrád-Csanád County:** Domaszék, Mórászék, 7.VII.2022, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens, CVS); Szeged, Airport, 7.VII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens, CVS). **Pest County:** Örkény, Göbolyjárás, 27.VII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens, CVS), and Vacsi-földek, 27.VII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (5 specimens, CVS); Pusztavacs, along road no. 5, 27.VII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (2 specimens, CVS); Tatárszentgyörgy, canal no. 20, 27.VII.2021, leg. V. Szénási (3 specimens, CVS).

Notes – The species occurs in Southern Europe (GERMANN 2018, GERMANN & NEMES 2019), and it was recorded as new to Hungary in 2018 (SZÉNÁSI 2018); subsequently it has been expanding rapidly.

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REFERENCES

- ALONSO-ZARAZAGA M. A., BARRIOS H., BOROVEC R., BOUCHARD P., CALDARA R., COLONNELLI E., GÜLTEKIN L., HLAVÁČ P., KOROTYAEV B., LYAL C. H. C., MACHADO A., MEREGALLI M., PIEROTTI H., REN L., SÁNCHEZ-RUIZ M., SFORZI A., SILFVERBERG H., SKUHROVEC J., TRÝZNA M., VELÁZQUEZ DE CASTRO A. J. & YUNAKOV N. N. 2017: *Cooperative Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera Curculionoidea. Monografías electrónicas SEA, vol. 8.* – Sociedad Entomológica Aragonesa (S. E. A.), Zaragoza, 729 pp.
- GERMANN C. 2018: A review of *Conocetus* Desbrochers des Loges, 1875, subgenus of *Polydrusus* Germar, 1817 (Coleoptera, Curculionidae, Entiminae). – *Europaeen Journal of Taxonomy* **392**: 1–39. <https://doi.org/10.5852/ejt.2018.392>
- GERMANN C. & NEMES T. 2019: First records of *Polydrusus* (*Conocetus*) *crinipes* Germann, 2018, from Croatia and Albania (Coleoptera, Curculionidae). – *Natura Croatia* **28**(1): 177–180. <https://doi.org/10.20302/NC.2019.28.17>
- PODLUSSÁNY A., SZÉNÁSI V. & MERKL O. 2019: Checklist of the Curculionoidea of Hungary (Coleoptera). – *Folia entomologica hungarica* **80**: 89–230. <https://doi.org/10.17112/FoliaEntHung.2019.80.89>
- PODLUSSÁNY A., SZITA É., LUPTÁK R., SZÉNÁSI V. & KISS B. 2014: Four weevil species new to the fauna of Hungary from motorway rest areas (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). – *Folia entomologica hungarica* **75**: 73–78. <https://doi.org/10.17112/FoliaEntHung.2014.75.873>
- PODLUSSÁNY A. & VIG K. 2021: *Az Alpokalja ormányosalkatú bogárfaunája (Coleoptera: Curculionoidea). [Curculionoidea of Alpokalja.]* – Savaria Megyei Hatókörű Városi Múzeum, MTA Vas Megyei Tudományos Testülete, Szombathely, 479 pp.
- SZÉNÁSI V. 2018: New weevils from Hungary and Slovakia (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). – *Folia entomologica hungarica* **79**: 77–80. <https://doi.org/10.17112/FoliaEntHung.2018.79.877>
- SZÉNÁSI V. 2020: Further new and rare weevils in Hungary (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). – *Folia entomologica hungarica* **81**: 81–86. <https://doi.org/10.17112/FoliaEntHung.2020.81.81>
- SZÉNÁSI V. 2022: A new species of the genus *Curculio* Linnaeus, 1758 (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) from Hungary and the Balkan Peninsula. – *Zootaxa* **5162**(5): 583–592. <https://doi.org/10.11646/Zootaxa.5162.5.8>
- SZÉNÁSI V. & VÁRI G. 2019: *Alcidodes karelinii* new to Hungary (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Molytinae). – *Folia entomologica hungarica* **80**: 83–87. <https://doi.org/10.17112/FoliaEntHung.2019.80.83>